

HiDyVe

Highly Dynamic Virtual and
Hybrid Validation and Verification

WP230

Future Communication Analysis

University of Bremen – TZI

Technical Report

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Management Summary

This technical report summarises research results obtained by the team at the University of Bremen during project HiDyVe. This part of our research is focussed on suitable communication mechanisms for performing virtual tests in the cloud. The test types investigated are (a) module tests of avionics software and (b) system tests for avionics controller networks with suitable simulations. The latter required the use of the Airbus ED-247 protocol. As a result of our investigations, we recommend the cloud-native infrastructure layer Kubernetes for effective concurrent execution of large module test campaigns in the cloud. For system testing, Kubernetes is not suitable. Instead, the Docker Compose + macvlan framework provides a lightweight, scriptable means for orchestrating multi-container applications with deterministic IP networking, as is essential for avionics system testing and simulation networks based on ED-247.

Preface

This technical report summarises research results obtained by the team at the University of Bremen during project HiDyVe. This part of our research is focussed on suitable communication mechanisms in the context of ultra-complex, potentially autonomous transportation systems.¹

[About this technical report](#)

At the start of the project, Airbus clarified that the focus of the communication analysis should be on **communication methods for module tests and system tests performed in a cloud simulation environment**. Airbus did not show interest in potential new communication means for autonomous aerial vehicles, since the existing techniques are deemed to be sufficient. In contrast to this, communication in the cloud for performing large-scale testing campaigns in trustworthy simulation environments that are fit for obtaining certification credit are currently of considerable interest and has not been researched in a comprehensive way until today.²

It was further decided that the communication analysis should be narrowed down to

[Focus on software module tests and on system tests](#)

- large-scale software module testing campaigns that could be performed concurrently in the cloud, and
- system tests in cloud simulation environments where virtualised communicating Aircraft (A/C) controllers and their virtualised peripherals could be tested in complex system integration scenarios.

The first application is mainly interesting for Airbus suppliers who wish to speed up their software testing campaigns and allow for a larger number

¹See our technical report [8] for the definition of terms and further details about this type of systems.

²See our discussion about the importance of cloud-based testing in [8, Chapter 19].

of test cases to be executed to increase test strength.³ The second application is of main interest for Airbus itself and helps to and speed up system integration test processes in virtualised environments.

The main results of the communication analysis can be summarised as follows.

Main
results
regarding
communication
analysis in
the cloud

- For concurrent module testing, the communication mechanisms offered by the **cloud-native infrastructure layer Kubernetes**⁴ is most appropriate.
- For running system integration tests in a simulation environment, Kubernetes is less suitable. Instead, alternative cloud-native infrastructures and orchestration approaches like **Docker Compose with Macvlan** are much more effective.

These results are described in more detail below.

³See our detailed technical report [2].

⁴<https://kubernetes.io>

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Chapter 1

Module Testing in the Cloud With Kubernetes

The theoretical foundations of the module testing methods we developed during project HiDyVe have been described elsewhere [1, 2, 4, 5, 7]. Here, we focus on the deployment of concurrent module tests in the cloud. This can be tried out with our experimental Kubernetes cluster for module testing in the cloud¹. Its utilisation is free for research purposes.

Module
testing

The essential strategy for concurrent module testing in the cloud uses the Kubernetes design pattern for **exposed load balancing server** with backend services performing the test-related tasks, as shown in Fig. 1.1. Clients access the test services by means of a static exposed IP address (or the registered name of the load balancing server), using **Representational State Transfer (REST) commands**² over the HTTP protocol. This is the preferred way of communication with and between Kubernetes-based services.

Concurrent
module
tests in
the cloud

The load balancer receives each request and relays it to a service backend that specialises in handling the specific type of request. The service backends are replicated. They can be accessed (again REST over HTTP) by means of a **cluster IP** address and a virtualised port number that can be used for each replicated instance. The underlying load balancing mech-

¹<https://fsmtestcloud.informatik.uni-bremen.de>

²<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/REST>

anism of Kubernetes distributes requests to different physical instances, resolving the cluster IP and virtual port number to concrete addresses.

Figure 1.1: Kubernetes server with load balancing for back-end services.

In our current setup, users can access a range of test services that support the module testing process:

- automated test case generation from finite state machine models,
- automated test case generation from symbolic finite state machine models³,
- automated learning of symbolic state machine models and model checking of module properties by means of the grey-box checking method [2],

Available
cloud
services
for
module
testing

³These are more expressive than finite state machine models, since they allow for guard conditions over input variables and output expressions over input and output variables.

- Test procedure execution in the cloud, running the generated test cases against the module under tests.

Recall from [8, Section 19.2] that software modules need to be executed in containers running Virtual Prototype (VP), so that the original machine code of the compiled module can be used. This is essential for obtaining certification credit for the executed tests.

Summarising, Kubernetes is well-suited for concurrent module testing in the cloud. The use of REST commands over HTTP offers a simple and widely adopted communication protocol, while Kubernetes' load balancing mechanisms ensure scalable, efficient distribution of testing workloads across replicated backend services.

Chapter 2

System Testing in the Cloud With Docker Compose And Macvlan

Recall that in modern avionics, controllers deployed in an **A/C** communicate over Ethernet twisted pair wires and switches, using the Avionics Full-Duplex Switched Ethernet (**AFDX**) protocol¹. Some controllers perform internal computations only, but others input sensor data and drive actuators to control peripherals.

**AFDX
networks**

Consequently, any suitable system test environment needs to provide

**Avionics
system
test
environments**

- **AFDX** communication or a suitable simulation thereof,
- sensor simulations providing input to the controllers,
- data generators simulating external **AFDX** senders to the System Under Test (**SUT**),
- readers for actuator stimulations performed by the **SUT**, and
- checkers (sometimes called **test oracles**) for verifying that the **SUT** outputs are consistent with the expected results specified in the test cases performed.

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Avionics_Full-Duplex_Switched_Ethernet,<https://www.sae.org/standards/content/arinc664p7-1/>

Airbus and their suppliers have specified the **ED-247 Aerospace Data Exchange Protocol for Avionics System Test**² to be used as communication means in system test configurations. This provides the **AFDX** communication mechanisms needed by the **SUT** and allows to integrate simulations and checkers into the network. It also provides the means to connect to or simulate the typical sensor and actuator interfaces used by avionic controllers (discrete, analogue, ARINC 429 etc.).³

ED-247
protocol

A fundamental discrepancy between A/C system test environments and Kubernetes communication paradigms consists in the fact that **AFDX** networks use statically configured IP addresses and ports while Kubernetes Pods obtain IP addresses dynamically when activated. Therefore, cumbersome techniques have to be implemented on top of Kubernetes to re-create static IP networks. Moreover, typical Unique Selling Point (**USP**)s of Kubernetes – like dynamic creation of new pods to react on high work loads, re-activation after failure, or load balancing – are of no use for avionic networks, since these concepts simply do not exist and, therefore, would not facilitate their faithful representation in the cloud. Finally, the preferred communication mechanism of Kubernetes is based on **REST** and HTTP which are both not applicable in avionics networks. As a consequence, putting ED-247 support on top of Kubernetes will be extremely cumbersome, if not technically impossible, since, for example, Kubernetes would probably “ruin” all real-time capabilities offered by ED-247.

Why
Kubernetes
is not
suitable
for avionic
system
testing in
the cloud

That said, we recommend to avoid using full-fledged cloud-native infrastructure layer like Kubernetes for avionic system test simulations in the cloud. Instead a more lightweight service layer should be used on top of the cloud operating system that just supports

Docker
Compose
+
macvlan

- lightweight container orchestration,

²https://github.com/airbus/ED247_LIBRARY

³While it can be criticised that ED-247 is so specific for avionics that it will never have any cross-domain use (as, for example, provided by the Functional Mock-up Interface (**FMI**)), it has to be admitted that the requirements of avionic system tests are so specific that cross-domain solutions will probably not meet their essential requirements. In particular, ED-247 provides determinism, protocol fidelity, and certifiability, which are non-negotiable in avionics testing.

- the setup of static container network environments,
- container deployment framework for simulation, and
- an infrastructure for deterministic containerised testing.

Such a lightweight service layer is provided by **Docker Compose + macvlan**.

Docker Compose + macvlan provides a lightweight, scriptable framework for orchestrating multi-container applications with deterministic IP networking. Using Docker Compose, engineers can declaratively define and manage sets of containers, while the macvlan driver allows each container to be assigned a static IP address on a shared Layer 2 network segment. This enables precise simulation of networked systems – such as avionics controller networks – where fixed addressing and low-level protocol access (e.g., raw UDP/IP) are essential. Although lacking the dynamic service discovery and self-healing features of cloud-native platforms like Kubernetes, the Compose + macvlan combination is well suited for reproducible testbeds, protocol emulation, and timing-sensitive experiments in controlled environments. An **A/C** controller would now be represented by a container. The macvlan driver allows to assign IP multicast addresses as is required for redundant controllers receiving data via **AFDX**.

Summarising, Kubernetes is not suitable for creating faithful simulation environments for avionic system tests in the cloud. Instead light-weight frameworks like Docker Compose + macvlan should be used. These provide the typical capabilities to setup a virtual ED-247 network connecting avionic controller software and simulated peripherals.

Chapter 3

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Appendix A

Abbreviations

A/C Aircraft

ACAS Airborne collision avoidance system

ACWG Assurance Case Working Group

ADAS Advanced Driver Assistance Systems

ADS Automated Driving System

AEB Automated Emergency Braking System

AFDX Avionics Full-Duplex Switched Ethernet

AI Artificial Intelligence

A/IS Autonomous and Intelligent Systems

ALARP As Low As Reasonably Practicable (risk management principle)

ANN Artificial Neural Network

AOP Agent-Oriented Programming

AOSE Agent-Oriented Software Engineering

ATM Air Traffic Management

ATO Automated Train Operation

ATP Automated Train Protection

ATTOL Automatic Taxiing, Take-off, and Landing

AV Autonomous Vehicle

BIP Behavior, Interaction, Priority component framework

BIST Built-In Self Test

BDI Belief-Desire Intention (for agent programming)

BITE Built-in Test Equipment

BMWi Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy

BSI British Standards Institution

CAT Commercial Air Transport (passengers, cargo, mail)

CCP Coupon Collector's Problem

CGF Coverage-Guided Greybox Fuzzing

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

CP Conformal Prediction

CPS Cyber-Physical Systems

CTMC Continuous Time Markov Chain

DAL Design Assurance Level

DDT All of the real-time operational and tactical functions required to operate a vehicle in on-road traffic (Definition taken verbatim from [9].)

DFA Deterministic finite automaton

DL Deep Learning

DNN Deep Neural Network

DOT US Department of transportation

DP Driving policy

DSL Domain Specific Language

DTMC Discrete Time Markov Chain

DUV Design Under Verification

DTF Digital Twin Framework

EAI Embodied Artificial Intelligence

EASA European Union Aviation Safety Agency

ECU Electronic Control Unit (automotive domain)

E/E system Electrical and/or electronic system

ETCS European Train Control Systems

FAA Federal Aviation Administration of the USA

FMI Functional Mock-up Interface

FMVSS Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standards (USA)

FSM Finite State Machine

FT Fault Tree

GAN Generative adversarial network

GoA Grade of Automation

GSN Goal Structure Notation

GSMP Generalized Semi-Markov stochastic Process

HARA Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment

HIC Human in Command

HITL Human in the loop

HIL Hardware-in-the-Loop (testing)

HOA Hanoi Omega Automata

HRI Human Robot Interaction

HW Hardware

IA Impact Analysis

IID Independent and Identically Distributed

IMA Integrated Modular Avionics

IXL Railway Interlocking System

LBIST Logic Built-In Self Test

LIDAR Light Detection and Ranging device

LTL Linear Temporal Logic

MAPE Monitor, Analyse, Plan, Execute (execution cycle of autonomic managers)

MAS Multi-Agent System

MAV Micro Aerial Vehicles

MBSE Model-based Systems Engineering

MBT Model-based Testing

MC Markov Chain

MEM Minimal Endogenous Mortality principle: based on the idea that the introduction of a technical system should not significantly increase the death rate in society

MDP Markov Decision Process

MIL Model-in-the-Loop (testing)

ML Machine Learning

MRC minimal risk condition

NCAP New Car Assessment Programme

NHTSA National Highway Traffic Safety Administration

NN Neural Network

OE Original Equipment

OD Obstacle Detection

ODD Operational Design Domain

OGSA Open Grid Services Architecture

OMG Object Management Group

OSLC Open Services for Lifecycle Collaboration

PAS A Publicly Available Specification or PAS is a standardization document that closely resembles a formal standard in structure and format but which has a different development model. The objective of a Publicly Available Specification is to speed up standardization. PASs are often produced in response to an urgent market need.(This definition has been taken verbatim from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Publicly_Available_Specification.) A PAS is co-branded with the BSI (British Standards Institution). (<https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/our-services/developing-new-standards/Develop-a-PAS/what-is-a-pas/>)

PBT Property-Based Testing

PIM Platform Independent Model

POT Property-Oriented Testing

PSM Platform Specific Model

QoS Quality of Service

RAS Robotics and Autonomous Systems

RBC Radio Block Centre

ReLU Rectified Linear Unit

REST Representational State Transfer

RNN Recurrent Neural Networks

ROI Return of Investment

RQ Research Question

SAE Society of Automotive Engineers

SCSC Safety-Critical Systems Club (see <https://scsc.uk>)

SDF Simulation/Scene Description Format

SFSM Symbolic Finite State Machine

SiL Software-in-the-Loop (testing)

SIL Safety Integrity Level

SOAP Simple Object Access Protocol

SoS Systems of Systems

SOTIF Safety of the Intended Functionality

SPL Software Product Line

SUT System Under Test

SW Software

TAS Trustworthy Autonomous Systems

TCAS Traffic Alert and Collision Avoidance System

TQ Tool Qualification

TTC Time to Collision

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

UCL Upper Confidence Limit

UKRI UK Research and Innovation

UML Unified Modelling Language

USM Utility State Machine

USP Unique Selling Point

UTM Unmanned Aircraft System Traffic Management

VBI Vehicle Behaviour Interface

VLSS Vehicle level safety strategy

VP Virtual Prototype

VRU Vulnerable Road User

V&V Verification and Validation

V2X Vehicle to Infrastructure (communication)

WCET Worst Case Execution Time

WP Work Package

WPBS Work Package Break-down Structure

XAI Explainable Artificial Intelligence

XMI XML Metadata Interchange

XML Extensible Markup Language

Appendix B

Glossary

Accident An unexpected event that causes damage, injury, or harm. See also **incident**

Adaptivity The ability to improve performance by learning from experience. [In the Machine Learning context], a system is considered adaptive when it continues to learn in real-time operation

Artificial intelligence (AI) Technology that appears to emulate human performance typically by learning, coming to its own conclusions, appearing to understand complex content, engaging in natural dialogues with people, enhancing human cognitive performance (also known as cognitive computing) or replacing people on execution of non-routine tasks. Applications include autonomous vehicles, automatic speech recognition and generation, and detection of novel concepts and abstractions (useful for detecting potential new risks and aiding humans to quickly understand very large bodies of ever-changing information)

Artificial neural network (ANN) A computational graph that consists of connected nodes ('neurons') that define the order in which operations are performed on the input. Neurons are connected by edges, which are parameterised by weights (and biases). Neurons are organised in layers, specifically an input layer, several intermediate layers, and an output layer. This document refers to a specific type of neural

network that is particularly suited to process image data: convolutional neural networks (CNNs) which use parameterised convolution operations to compute their outputs. Commonly used types of neural networks are to be highlighted: **Convolutional neural networks (CNNs)**, **Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)**, **Generative adversarial networks (GANs)**

Automation The use of control systems and information technologies reducing the need for human input, typically for repetitive tasks

Autonomy The ability to perform tasks in complex environments without input by a human

Avionics Electronics (including computers), as applied in aviation

Bias An error from erroneous assumptions in the learning [process]. High bias can cause an algorithm to miss the relevant relations between attributes and target outputs (=underfitting)

Big Data A new technology, which allows the analysis of big amount of data (more than terabytes), with a high velocity (high speed of data processing), from various sources (sensors, images, texts, etc.), and which might be unstructured (not standardised format)

Brittle (deep neural network) A trained DNN is called brittle if seemingly small changes in the input data lead to drastic changes in the output, resulting, for example, in an erroneous image classification

cloud-native repository A data archive residing in the cloud which can be evaluated and manipulated in the cloud as well, without the necessity to download this data to local computers

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) - a specialised kind of neural network for processing data that has a known grid-like topology. Convolutional networks use convolution [a specialised kind of linear operation] in place of general matrix multiplication in at least one of their layers

DARPA (Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency) A US Government Agency whose mission is to make pivotal investments in breakthrough technologies for national security

Data for safety (EASA) Data4Safety (also known as D4S) is a data collection and analysis programme that supports the goal of ensuring the highest common level of safety and environmental protection for the European aviation system. The programme aims at collecting and gathering all data that may support the management of safety risks at European level. This includes safety reports (or occurrences), flight data (i.e. data generated by the aircraft via the flight data recorders), surveillance data (air traffic data), weather data - but those are only a few from a much longer list. As for the analysis, the programme's ultimate goal is to help to 'know where to look' and to 'see it coming'. In other words, it will support the performance-based environment and set up a more predictive system. More specifically, the programme will facilitate better knowledge of where the risks are (safety issue identification), determine the nature of these risks (risk assessment) and verify whether the safety actions are delivering the needed level of safety (performance measurement). It aims to develop the capability to discover vulnerabilities in the system across terabytes of data

Data science A broad field that refers to the collective processes, theories, concepts, tools and technologies that enable the review, analysis and extraction of valuable knowledge and information from raw data

Data-driven AI The data-driven [approach] focuses on building a system that can [learn] what is the right answer based on having [trained on] a large number of [labelled] examples

Deep learning (DL) A specific type of machine learning based on the use of large neural networks to learn abstract representations of the input data by composing many layers

Digital twin *"A digital twin is a virtual representation that serves as the*

*real-time digital counterpart of a physical object or process.*¹

Embodied artificial intelligence (EAI) In EAI, AI algorithms learn through embodied physical interactions with their environments, whether real or simulated

Epistemologic defeaters Conditions or events leading to the loss, reduction, or prevention of some positive epistemic status, that is, conditions or events counting *against* a belief

Epistemology The study of knowledge and the justification of beliefs

Explainable AI “*is artificial intelligence (AI) in which the results of the solution can be understood by humans.*”²

Functional safety is the part of the overall safety of a system or piece of equipment that depends on automatic protection operating correctly in response to its inputs or failure in a predictable manner (fail-safe). The automatic protection system should be designed to properly handle likely human errors, systematic errors, hardware failures and operational/environmental stress.³

Generative adversarial networks (GANs) - a type of construct in neural network technology that is composed of two neural networks: a generative network and a discriminative network. These work together to provide high-level simulation of conceptual tasks

Illocutionary force The intention of the sender in a message exchanged between agents

Impact analysis (also change impact analysis) “*is the analysis of changes within a deployed product or application and their potential consequences*”.⁴

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_twin

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Explainable_artificial_intelligence

³definition adopted verbatim from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_safety

⁴https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Change_impact_analysis

- Incident** Any unexpected event that does not result in serious losses or injury, but *might* have caused an accident. For formally, an incident occurs if a system reaches a hazardous state from which it recovers without entering an accident state before
- Inference** The process of feeding the machine learning model an input and computing its output. See also related definition of ‘Training’
- Internet of things (IoT)** The network of physical objects that contain embedded technology to communicate and sense or interact with their internal states or the external environment
- Machine learning (ML)** Rooted in statistics and mathematical optimisation, machine learning is the ability of computer systems to improve their performance by exposure to data without the need to follow explicitly programmed instructions. [Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence]. Machine learning strategies go by three methods **Supervised learning**, **Unsupervised learning** and **Reinforcement learning**
- Machine learning model** A parametrised function that maps inputs to outputs. The parameters are determined during the training process
- minimal risk condition** Vehicle state in order to reduce the risk of harm, when a given trip cannot be completed
- Mode confusion** The actual system state differs from what a responsible human (e.g. driver, pilot) thinks the state is (e.g. pilot thinks that auto pilot is active while it is actually switched off)
- Model-driven AI** Model-driven AI (or symbolic AI), instead, attempts to capture knowledge and derive decisions through explicit representation and rules
- Narrow AI** Artificial intelligence that is focused on one narrow task

Neural network A computational graph that consists of connected nodes ('neurons') that define the order in which operations are performed on the input. Neurons are connected by edges, which are parameterised by weights (and biases). Neurons are organised in layers, specifically an input layer, several intermediate layers, and an output layer. This document refers to a specific type of neural network that is particularly suited to process image data: convolutional neural networks (CNNs) which use parameterised convolution operations to compute their outputs. Commonly used types of neural networks are to be highlighted: **Convolutional neural networks (CNNs)**, **Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)**, **Generative adversarial networks (GANs)**

Open Services for Lifecycle Collaboration (OSLC) is an open community creating specifications for *interactions between tools*. The objective is to facilitate the development of IDEs, including issue tracking, testing, and other services relevant for the lifecycle of software-based products. In particular, IDEs should become more flexible with the help of OSLC, so that it will become easier to integrate tools of other providers, as long as these tools conform to the data exchange protocols provided by OSLC

Operational safety means the absence of unreasonable risk under the occurrence of hazards resulting from functional insufficiencies of the intended functionality (e.g. false/missed detection), operational disturbances (e.g. environmental conditions like fog, rain, shadows, sunlight, infrastructure) or by reasonably foreseeable misuse/errors by the driver, passengers and other road users (safety hazards — without system faults).⁵

Performative same meaning as *illocutionary force*

Predictability/determinism A system is predictable/deterministic if when given identical inputs, produces identical outputs

⁵definition adopted verbatim from <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/operational-safety>

- Rebutting defeater** A defeater (in epistemology) providing evidential support for the opposite thesis of a belief
- Recurrent neural networks (RNNs)** - a type of advanced artificial neural network (ANN) that involves directed cycles in memory. One aspect of recurrent neural networks is the ability to build on earlier types of networks with fixed-size input vectors and output vectors
- Reinforcement learning** In this algorithm, the neural network is reinforced for positive results, and punished for a negative result, forcing the neural network to learn over time
- Resilience** Attribute of systems and applications to ensure high service availability through monitoring and automatic adjustment of redundant or virtualized infrastructure components
- Road furniture (also street furniture)** A collective term for objects and pieces of equipment installed along streets and roads for various purposes. It includes benches, traffic barriers, bollards, post boxes, phone boxes, streetlamps, traffic lights, traffic signs, bus stops, tram stops, taxi stands, public lavatories, fountains, watering troughs, memorials, public sculptures, and waste receptacles
- Robustness** For an input varying in a region of the state space, the system is producing the same outputs
- Safety science** A broad field that refers to the collective processes, theories, concepts, tools and technologies that support safety management
- Safing mission** A behaviour triggered when sudden events increase the risk in an unacceptable way. The objective of this behaviour is to transfer the system into a stable safe state as quickly as possible [6]
- Supervised learning** - the process of learning a function that maps an input to an output based on example input-output training samples

Training The process of optimising the parameters (weights) of a machine learning model given a data set and a task to achieve on that data set. For example, in supervised learning, the training data consists of input (e.g. an image) / output (e.g. a class label) pairs and the machine learning model 'learns' the function that maps the input to the output, by optimising its internal parameters. See also related definition of 'Inference'

Undercutting defeater A defeater (in epistemology) removing support for a belief

Unsupervised learning - this strategy is used in cases where there is no labelled data set available to learn from. The neural network analyses the data set, and then a cost function tells the neural network how far off target it was. The neural network then adjusts to increase accuracy of the algorithm

Variance An error from sensitivity to small fluctuations in the training set. High variance can cause an algorithm to model the random noise in the training data, rather than the intended outputs (=overfitting)

Vehicle to everything (V2X) communication Communication between a (potentially autonomous) vehicle and "*any entity that may affect, or may be affected by, the vehicle.*"⁶

Vulnerable Road User (VRU) A road user who is not occupying a vehicle such as a passenger car, a public transit vehicle, or a train

A part of this glossary has been adopted verbatim from [3].

⁶<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vehicle-to-everything>